

Literacy training

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Аннотация: В данной научной статье полностью разъясняются правовые правила обучения грамоте учащихся начальных классов, повышения интереса детей к письму и чтению, правила правильного письма и красивого написания букв без орфографических ошибок.

Ключевые слова: Обращая внимание на правила правильного письма, красивого и беглого письма, словарное значение слова эссе, звучание, фонетику, виды эссе, вежливость.

Abstract: In this scientific article, the legal rules of teaching literacy to elementary school students, increasing children's interest in writing and reading, and the rules for writing correctly and spelling letters beautifully without spelling mistakes are fully explained.

Key words: Paying attention to the rules of correct writing, beautiful and fluent writing, the dictionary meaning of the word essay, sound, phonetics, types of essays, courtesy.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga savod o'rgatishning qonun qoidalari bolalarni yozishga va o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqishlarini oshirish va to'g'ri behato yozish hamda, harflarni imlo hatosiz chiroyli yozish qoidalari haqida to'liq yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: To'g'ri yozish qoidalari, chiroyli va behato yozish, insho

soʻzining lugʻaviy maʼnosi, tovush, fonetika, insho turlari, husnixatga eʼtibor qaratish.

Reading and writing is a type of speech activity of a person, reading and writing skills are also other types of speech activity, oral storytelling, hearing and understanding the speech of others, internal speech is formed in an integral connection with the formation of skills. a certain activity is required to be repeated many times. Therefore, in the process of teaching literacy, the child needs to read and write a lot. Our writing is considered sound writing, the stage of converting graphic characters (letters) into sounds in reading is the opposite, the step of converting sounds into letters in writing, which makes reading and writing much more difficult, causing the need to analyze the word by sound-letter. releases Literacy teaching methodology takes into account the features of the phonetic system of the Uzbek language when informing students about sounds. To teach literacy, it is necessary to know the sounds that serve to distinguish the meanings of words, that is, phonemes. At school, literacy is taught using the analytical-synthetic sound method. By analyzing a word, students separate the necessary sounds, analyze them, synthesize them, and on this basis learn the process of reading letters and syllables. In this case, it is necessary to take into account the graphic system of the language, the characteristics of marking sounds in writing. In the teaching of literacy, the principle of syllabic teaching is adopted. Therefore, in the first days of learning to read, students are taught to read with syllabic reading in mind. When teaching literacy, it is necessary to take into account that the letters of the Uzbek alphabet are used in four versions (printed and written, capital and small letters). Reading and writing is a complex psycho-physiological process. A

child who is just starting to read and write cannot turn the movements of the elements into a single movement, so each element is an independent movement, which is sometimes a very difficult psychological process.

It requires not only mental attention, but also physical movement. Adding sounds in teaching reading is a difficult task. Many students pronounce sounds separately, but cannot form syllables. To overcome this difficulty, it is necessary to pay attention to the development of speech organs. During the initial writing process, they perform many independent activities: holding a pen correctly put it right. learning to write a letter, taking into account its shape, elements, and lines, taking into account the lines of the notebook, remembering how to move the pen along the line: When writing a word, knowing how to add a letter to a letter and the word's ability to fit into one line If it doesn't work, remember to sit straight without looking too close to the notebook. In the old school, reading and writing were not taught at the same time, only reading was taught. Reading was not even learned at the same time as writing with the (syllable in) method. Teaching to read is called "ancient". This method has remained unchanged for centuries. The Russian-style schools opened in Turkestan played a positive role in teaching literacy to a certain extent. The method of teaching Uzbek writing and literacy in the Uzbek classes of Russian-style schools was gradually reformed starting from 1900: from the Khija method. switched to the phonetic method. From the 1900s, the teachers of Uzbek classes of the Russian-system school used the Tatar alphabet based on the phonetic method. The language and content of this book were not suitable for Uzbek classes. In 1902, the native language alphabet "Ustodi avval" was published according to Saidrasul Saidazizov's sound method requirements.

After the publication of "Master First" a new era began in teaching Uzbek literacy. The sound method was completely different from the old method of teaching literacy and made teaching easier. turned into lim. "Master first" consists of three sections: the first section is the alphabet period, in modern terms. In this section, the author noted that the letters of the Arabic alphabet are not in alphabetical order, but the pronunciation of the sound represented by the letter is easy and difficult, and the writing of the letters is simple or complicated. The author took into account that the occurrence of several different forms of this letter in writing makes it difficult to teach literacy: at the beginning of the alphabet period, he gave letters that are almost always used in the same form, and letters whose form varies depending on the place of writing at the beginning of words, in the middle of the word, at the end of the word, and finally, given a separate form of writing, suitable examples are given. For example, to introduce the letter q, he chose the words snow, sleep, and white, and to introduce the letter g, he chose the words cave, mountain, and so on. The author followed the principle of simple to complex and gradually complicated the alphabet period. In the alphabet section of the book, he selected words from the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. The book "Muradod" was used to teach writing and to develop good writing skills. All three types of exercises are given in this booklet, as well as essay samples in some editions. In the schools of the Russian system, the teaching of reading and writing usually started at the same time and were carried out in close connection with each other; every day there was first reading and then writing class. Reading and writing are taught based on the principle of consciousness, children clearly imagine which sound, syllable, word or sentence they are reading or writing. He understood the

meaning, he consciously knew that he was writing the single form of Arabic letters, the form depending on the place of use in a word, or the element of a letter.

K.D. It was founded by Ushensky and developed by introducing it to the primary classes of Russian schools. At the beginning of this century, this method began to enter newly popular schools in Turkestan through Russian-style schools. Based on this method, plans and programs, textbooks and manuals were published, and children's literacy began to be published. The traditional principles of this method are as follows: 1) Analytical-synthetic sound method in literacy teaching is educational and developmental in nature, based on the purpose of forming a person, it develops the mind through a system of analytical-synthetic exercises and speech exercises. takes into account the age characteristics of students. 2) The analytical-synthetic sound method is divided into the first, pre-alphabetic (preparatory) period, alphabetic period and the last period after the alphabet; secondly, teaching to write goes simultaneously with teaching to read - in parallel. 3). Analytical-synthetic sound method from a psychological-linguistic point of view: firstly, literacy training is based on the speech skills acquired by live observation of children: secondly, literacy training is based on sound, in which it is necessary to separate sound, analyze and synthesize it, the articulation of sounds, great importance is given to the development of children's phonemic hearing, from the third the syllable is taken as a unit of study; in this, great attention is paid to working on the syllable (syllable, reading the table of syllables).

In literacy training, the initial interview exercises are conducted in the following order:

1. Conversation on the picture.

2. Extracting sentences suitable for analysis from the conversation.
3. Divide the sentence into words.
4. Dividing the word into syllables.
5. To separate the sound from the syllable.
6. Explanation of sound pronunciation.
7. Finding the learned sound from different words.
8. Introducing the learned new sound form - letter.
9. Making syllables and words from hyphens.

The first week of the literacy period is devoted to preparing students for literacy, so this period is called pre-alphabet. During this period of literacy training, a conversation is organized based on the above methods based on the pictures on pages 3-6 of the alphabet book, and a conscious attitude to one's own speech is formed.

List of used literature:

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